

Academic publishing in turmoil: Disentangling and opening up access to and valuation of scientific knowledge

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Ongoing debates on the hegemonic structures of academic publishing have to be regarded in the broader context of scientific knowledge production and its valuation. Increasingly we see resistance emerging against the monopolization and entanglement of both quality measurement indicators and high impact publishing. The open movement offers alternatives for engagement and evaluation in scholarly communication.

"What science becomes in any historical era depends on what we make of it"
Sandra Harding

Parasitic gatekeeping: how the dense entanglement of access and evaluation creates perverse knowledge markets

Bibliometrics, the statistical analysis of publications and authors, has become integral to contemporary academic life. Often used uncritically by decision makers and researchers alike to assess scientific quality and performance, the metric tide (<https://responsiblemetrics.org/the-metric-tide/>) has already been built into academic reward and incentive structures. In some fields, this means no tenure without a publication in Nature, Science or Cell, all journals with a high reputation that is mirrored by their high journal impact factor. Such simplistic, metrics-based evaluation of scientific quality enforces the rigid and hegemonic structure of scientific publishing and scholarly communication. It is part of a highly elaborate hierarchy of academic output that is ingrained in abstract and citation databases, university rankings and scientific search engines. In addition, such an incentive system pushes scholars to produce an abundance of high-impact publications with positive outcomes and seemingly novel findings. Getting research published might even become more important than getting research right. This in turn leads to more publications and an increased need for assessment tools and ever more metrics.

Three knowledge databases currently serve as the main guardians of citation counting and impact measurement in research: Web of Science (recently sold by Thomson Reuters to a group of private equity funds), Scopus (Elsevier), and Google Scholar. Besides gathering information about scientific publications and citations, all of them are also providers of access to knowledge. Their parent companies publish scientific journals or provide publishing infrastructures, make content searchable and findable and offer other information products such as discovery services. Why is this entanglement, indeed this dependency of access to knowledge and its evaluation, so apparently alarming? On the one hand, it makes sense that only an organization with the technical means to store this vast array of information could develop the means to order it and then to label it with a value. On the other hand, such a situation creates a worrying concentration of power and market logics.

Controlling the output and the definition of value

The core business model is to sell access to content, be it research articles or indices and rankings of the publication landscape. Since the 1990s, this business has grown enormously: American research libraries, for example, have had to increase their budget for scientific journal subscriptions by 400 per cent in the last 25 years (Larivière et al 2015). This highly profitable business model is based on the symbolic power that the journals have as gatekeepers of scientific quality assessment and performance measuring. The business model involves not just providing access but also using indicators to rank the accessible content. Such rankings were developed in times of information overload as tools that were able to access high quality scholarly communication (Garfield 1979) in a way similar to Google's search algorithms, but much more simplistic. However, these tools for

identifying relevant scholarly publications were soon transformed into guardians of quality and indicators of performance. Many scientific careers and institutional rankings depend on these numbers. This makes the system especially vulnerable to trickery and subversion. Besides citation scams, WoS and Scopus are also prone to abuse by predatory journals (<https://scholarlyoa.com/2014/07/22/life-science-journal-delisted-from-scopus/>). This situation thus reveals the deficiency of metrics that are based on partial data and biased collections, and suggests that such a universalist approach to measuring scientific quality might be the wrong one altogether.

On top of this, an oligopoly of five publishing corporations (incl. Elsevier) currently controls 50 per cent of all journal articles, enjoying high profit margins (Larivière et al 2015). In recent years, this oligopoly has substantially increased the access fees to their portfolios without providing much added benefit to the authors, research institutions and tax-payers that mainly fund their business. For this reason, there is growing unrest about the legitimacy of the monopolised and untransparent flow of capital from public to private (Lawson et al. 2015), and the parasitic behaviour of publishers who bleed their hosts after having captured them in a highly elaborate but self-referential system of evaluation.

A flawed basis for evaluation, high prices for access, few services or benefits for authors and funders: these form the basis of rampant discontent among academic communities and policy makers, especially since the Open Access movement has already proven that there is a way to begin disentangling access to knowledge and its evaluation.

“Old wine in new bottles,” or true change?’

At its most basic, open access means making research outputs available online free of cost and free of most restrictions on copying and reuse. However, with the discovery of open access as business model by the publishing industry (including predatory publishers) in a world of "publish or perish," its radiance has somewhat suffered. Due to high article processing charges, some scientists have become aware of the cost of publishing for the first time. They worry about having to apply for additional funding and about added bureaucracy and pressure. Furthermore, and in a way that piggybacks on fears of the metric tide, OA is often confused with lack of peer review (<http://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2013/10/07/whos-afraid-of-open-access/>), low impact factors, or even with copyright infringement. This is especially true in the context of fake or predatory publishers. In communities not already fond of OA publishing and in institutions lacking a strong open policy, much effort is still needed to throw light on the positive aspects of OA. On the other hand, the Gold OA business model – authors pay for their articles to be open access (article processing charges APCs) – has accelerated negotiations amongst policy makers, academia and industry and has led to a widespread implementation of OA policies (e.g. in US or EU funding schemes). But the golden route to open access is met with suspicion, if there is no additional services for the money by corporate publishers, and just prolongues the fact that tax payers have to pay twice, for the research and its publication. Nevertheless, OA helps to disentangle access and evaluation, since the content is now accessible without the pre-formatted access regime.

However, we need to understand OA not as an end in itself, but as merely the beginning of a veritable revolution in scholarly communication. Open access is the basis for many aspects of open science. In order to foster the idea of openness, we need to start training ourselves in open skills and ideas of sharing that go beyond the traditional dissemination of research output, but also beyond the technocratic ideas about liberation that mainly focus on change via technology. (<http://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2016/07/26/how-can-we-build-a-human-centered-open-science/>) We need much more than an open-washing of traditional models of knowledge production and dissemination.

Alternative visions for open scholarly communication: disentangling access and valuation

Consortially funded OA (Like the Open Library of the Humanities <https://www.openlibhums.org/>, or SCOAP3 <https://scoap3.org/>) is a good example of innovative concepts of sharing knowledge and risk, and is another important step in the creation of alternative publishing markets that will further disentangle evaluation from access to knowledge.

Phases of transition to OA will necessarily require strong visions, concrete open policies and the monitoring of cost transparency and negotiations. (<https://zenodo.org/record/34079?ln=en>) Policy makers, academia and industry all need to understand the complimentary opportunities that commercial markets and knowledge commons offer. At the same time, stakeholders in the transition process need to consider innovative forms of quality and impact assessment that go beyond simplistic or flawed metrics, and which are inspired by the many shades of openness of science in society (see [Leiden manifesto: http://www.leidenmanifesto.org/](http://www.leidenmanifesto.org/)).

Industry is quickly learning from (or harvesting) the ideas of the open science movement. The time is now to think about relevant reward and business models. To reward the efforts of making research data openly available We need models that do more than mimic existing models like citeable "data papers". For example, we will have to discuss open licences that provide scalable approaches to evaluating contribution in systems of mass collaboration, respecting community norms as well as legal impact with regard to enforced copyright legislation. Authors, researchers and stakeholders alike should participate in defining what added value means in open science realms, and what is needed to turn parasites into collaborators.

What do we want science to become? The Vienna Principles are an example of a shared vision for the future of scholarly communication, designed to provide a coherent frame of reference for the debate on how to improve the current system. Comments are welcome via viennaprinciples.org.

Vienna PRINCIPLES

a vision for scholarly communication

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| 1 Accessibility | 5 Transparency | 9 Evaluation |
| 2 Discoverability | 6 Understandability | 10 Validated Progress |
| 3 Reusability | 7 Collaboration | 11 Innovation |
| 4 Reproducibility | 8 Quality Assurance | 12 Public Good |

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